

PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION OF TERMS

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Abstract. This article discusses the problem of translation of complex Internet terms (including compound terms, phrases, abbreviations) from English into Russian and Uzbek.

Keywords: term, terminology, neoterm, concept, Internet, abbreviation.

INTRODUCTION

Terminology is a layer of vocabulary, a system of terms related to a particular field of production. A term is a word or phrase expressing a particular concept, and is mainly intended to express precise scientific concept¹. If a term is created and used by certain industry experts, and if this term expresses new meaning or notion, like a neologism, it is called “neoterm”. According to Dadabaev, “the Uzbek language in general, and its Internet terminology in particular, is like a complex sociotechnical system that works continuously and is constantly changing”².

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Internet terms can be divided by their structure: “a single-core term is a simple term, and if a term contains two or more cores – it is a complex term”. The problem of translation of complex Internet terms is in their diversity of functions and content. For example, the following complex Internet terms, function to name something: “cable local-area network” – «кабельная локальная сеть» - “кабелли маҳаллий тармоқ”; “card with magnetic strip” – «карта с магнитной полосой»- “магнит йўлли карта”; while the terms “Carrier Sense Multiple Access with Collision Detection (CSMA / CD)” – «Множественный доступ с контролем несущей и обнаружением коллизий - “кўпчилик томонидан эркин фойдаланиш”; “character based information system” – «Информационная система на основе символов» - “ахборотнинг нишонли тизими”; “classification of information and its bearers as secret” – «Отнесение информации и ее носителей к тайне» - “маълумотлар ва уларни ташувчиларни махфийлаштириш”; “Code Division Multiple Access” – “Кодовым разделением множественного доступа” - “кодли ажратишли

¹ Paluanova H.D. Ingliz, o‘zbek, rus va qoraqalpoq tillarida ekologik terminlarning derivatsion-semantik prinsiplari. Doctoral thesis. Tashkent, 2016.

² Dadaboev H. Xozirgi o‘zbek tili qurilishida o‘zbek tilining o‘rni. — Proceedings of Scientific-Theoretical Conference on Urgent Problems of Linguistics. Tashkent, 2015. P. 24-31.

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кўпчилик томонидан эркин фойдаланиш” function to describe. Moreover, the terms like “dual-homed gateway” – «двойной шлюз» - “икки уйли шлюз”; “e-development” – «Электронная разработка» - “АКТ ёрдамида тараққиёт”; “e-signature certificate user” – “имзо калити сертификати фойдаланувчиси”; “full-text database” – “тўла матнли маълумотлар базаси” function to define.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An analysis of the English Internet terminology of the joint form revealed that a certain group of these terms was originally formed in the general lexicon or other field terminology, and a method of “word-for-word” translation is used. For example, the term “Databank” is a combination of words “data” – “маълумотлар” and “bank” – “банк”, so it can be translated as “маълумотлар банки”. But, the term “backbone”, translated into Uzbek as “магистрал”, while it is derived from the combination of “back” – “орқа” and bone – “суяк”.

The problem of translation of combinational terms has always been one of the most pressing issues in the theory of translation and in the theory of terminology. There are cases, when it is necessary to translate Internet terms consisting of 4 words: “insurance form of information protection” – “ахборот муҳофазасининг суғурта шакли”, “Integrated Services Digital Network” - “хизматлари бирлашган рақамли тармоқ”, “interactive television operating system” – “ўзаро фаол телекўрсатувлар операцион тизими” and so on.

Most of the two-component Internet terms are formed by the preposition “of”. For example, the term “minimum of privilege” - “энг кам имтиёзлар” means one of the basic principles of the organization of protection system in Internet terminology, in which each subject has the least privileges to perform the tasks assigned to him. In some cases, in the process of translation of two-component Internet terms from English into Uzbek one of the components stayed unchanged completely: “Вануан тармоғи”, “Internet тармоғи”, “Internet этикети”, “Internet инфратузилмаси”, “Ethernet стандарти”, “Internet реклама”, “Internet банки”, “Internet трейдинг”, “Internet футурологияси”, “Internet провайдери”, “Ethernet технологияси” etc.

The first component of the two-component terminology may consist of acronyms: DNS server - DNS сервери, BGP protocol - BGP баённомаси, NSFNET network - NSFNET тармоғи, ISDN standard - ISDN стандарти, BRI interface - BRI интерфейси, CASE-system – CASE-тизими.

CONCLUSION

Abbreviations is another problematic field in the translation of Internet terms. They can be translated with the help of calling, semi-calling or finding

equivalents³. Examples include “CSNET - (Computer Science NETWORK)” – “компьютер илмий тармоғи”, “NSFNET” - (“National Science Foundation NETWORK”) - “миллий фан фонди тармоғи”, UUCPNET (Unix-to- Unix Copy) - “халқаро электрон почта”, “BACP” – (Bandwidth Allocation Control Protocol) - “ўтказиш қобилиятини ажратишинг бошқариш баённомаси”, “BGP” (Border Gateway Protocol) – “чегара тармоқлараро баённома”, “BIP” – (Bit Interleave Parity) - “битлар навбатланиши жуфтлиги”, or “хужжатлар услубияти семантикаси ва спецификасини белгиловчи тил”, etc.

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